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Effectiveness of the Maudsley Model of Anorexia Nervosa Treatment for Adults (MANTRA): A systematic review

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The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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Abstract

Background: Maudsley Model of Anorexia Nervosa Treatment for Adults (MANTRA) is recommended by NICE for the treatment of adults with anorexia nervosa (AN). However, despite this fact, the approach remains relatively understudied. The aim of this study was to systematically update the research evidence regarding the use of the MANTRA in the treatment of Eating Disorders (ED).

Method: The databases used were Web of Science, Scopus, and PsycInfo, including studies up to 31 May 2023. PRISMA guidelines were followed, and Cochrane tools were used to assess the risk of bias. The search focused on identifying published articles that

discussed the usefulness of MANTRA as a component of treatment for eating disorders, following PICO criteria.

Results: Nine studies spanning the period from 2011 to 2023 were included. Findings suggested that MANTRA was effective in improving body mass index (BMI), eating symptomatology and emotional state. There were generally no significant differences compared to other treatment conditions.

Limitations to interpreting this systematic review include the methodological quality of included studies and the elevated risk of bias.

Conclusions: This review was the first to examine the effectiveness of MANTRA. The results indicate that MANTRA has shown effectiveness similar to other treatments for adults AN patients in addressing key clinical variables. It has been used in different populations (adolescents, males, inpatients) and formats (group, online) However, more research is needed to determine its effectiveness.

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Keywords: anorexia nervosa; Maudsley Model of Anorexia Nervosa Treatment for Adults; MANTRA; intervention; systematic review.

1. INTRODUCTION

Anorexia nervosa (AN) is a serious mental disorder that affects mainly young females. AN is a disabling, deadly, and costly mental disorder that impairs physical health and disrupts psychosocial functioning (Treasure et al., 2020). Psychiatric comorbidity is very common in AN. Blinder et al. (2006) showed that amongst 2,436 female inpatients, 97% were diagnosed with at least one psychiatric comorbidity. A study review revealed that prevalent psychiatric comorbidities included anxiety (rates up to 62%), mood disorders (54%), and substance use disorders along with post-traumatic stress disorders, each demonstrating similar comorbidity (27%) (Hambleton et al., 2022). AN has one of the highest mortality rates amongst all psychiatric illnesses (Arcelus et al., 2011; Arija et al., 2022). The main causes of death are related to specific medical conditions as well as suicide (Ahn et al., 2019; Neumärker, 2000; Westmoreland et al., 2022). Many patients with very severe AN recover from their illness but AN also shows considerable long-term negative consequences. The results from a large clinical longitudinal study, with a large sample of AN inpatients (N= 1.693) and a subsample (N= 112), with 20-year follow-up, remission was found in 30% (total sample) and in 40% (subsample) (Fichter et al., 2017). In a recent systematic review, the relapse frequency was found to be 31% (Berends et al., 2018). Given the impairment in their quality of life, the high morbidity, relapses and mortality associated with AN, the development of an effective treatment is critical.

Respect to treatment and in accordance with the international evidence-based treatment guideline National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), psychological therapy is the first-choice treatment for eating disorders (NICE, 2020). These guidelines recommend that AN programmes should focus on nutritional and physical rehabilitation and in the provision of structured psychological treatment. Although there is a growing body of evidence that supports family treatment and enhanced cognitive behavioural therapy as proven, evidence-based and effective approaches for the treatment of adolescents and children (Dalle Grave et al., 2013; Le Grange et al., 2010; NICE, 2020), there is a lack of high-quality evidence to guide the clinician in the treatment of adults who have AN. The recommendation in adults would be an individual intervention including: individual focused cognitive behavioural therapy for the eating disorder (CBT-ED), the Specialist Supportive Clinical Management (SSCM) or the Maudsley Model of Treatment of Anorexia Nervosa for Adults (MANTRA).

MANTRA is a specialised integrative therapy that was developed specifically for chronic anorexic patients (Schmidt, Wade, & Treasure, 2014; Schmidt, Startup, & Treasure, 2018), and it is characterised by: (a) taking into account the biological factors involved in the development and maintenance of AN and trait-focused, drawing on neuropsychological, social cognitive and personality trait research; (b) including both intra- and interpersonal maintaining factors and strategies to address these; and (c) being modularised with a hierarchy of procedures, tailored to the need of the individual. (Schmidt et al., 2014).

MANTRA is based on the Cognitive Interpersonal Maintenance model of AN, which synthesises key internal and interpersonal maintaining factors (Schmidt & Treasure, 2006). The model includes four maintaining factors: rigid, detail-focused thinking with fear of mistakes; avoidant emotional processing; positive beliefs about anorexia's benefits; and enabling responses from close others. MANTRA intervenes in the emotional regulation and eating behaviour, emphasising behaviour change strategies to help patients transition from inpatient care to daily life and strengthen relationships.

MANTRA addresses cognitive, emotional, relational and biological factors maintaining AN by helping individuals find adaptive coping methods. This involves motivation to change, improving nutrition, addressing interpersonal difficulties, adopting healthier thinking styles, managing emotions, and forming an identity separate from AN. MANTRA is a flexible, manualised treatment consisting of seven core modules conducted over 20 to 40 individual weekly sessions depending on illness severity, plus 4 or 5 follow-up meetings (monthly). *Engagement and Psychoeducation* module emphasizes the importance of understanding the illness and its impact on the individual's life. In *Shared Formulation* the therapist and the individual work together to develop a shared understanding (formulation) of the factors contributing to the development and maintenance of the eating disorder. *Making Sense of the Illness* module involves helping the individual make sense of their experience with anorexia nervosa within the context of their life story and personal beliefs. *Finding Your Voice* focuses on enhancing the individual's ability to communicate their needs and desires effectively. *Active Change* module involves identifying and challenging specific behaviors and beliefs that maintain the eating disorder. *Relationships and Support* explores the impact of relationships on the individual's recovery journey, highlighting the importance of involving family members and significant others in the treatment process. The final module, *Ending and Transitions*, focuses on consolidating gains made during treatment and preparing for the transition to independent living. Throughout these seven modules patients engage in specific exercises as writing a letter to AN my friend and my enemy, the animal models regarding the parents' reaction, and the vicious flower, where each of the petals describes a factor that keeps locked into AN.

Which modules and factors are addressed in treatment depends on individual needs and preferences. In MANTRA motivational interviewing (Miller & Rollnick, 2002) is a central therapeutic technique, alongside tasks that promote emotional expression, mentalizing, perspective shifting, and compassionate self-view. MANTRA emphasizes collaboration, respect for autonomy, and guided self-care, using an easy-to-read workbook for patients and therapists to work together (Schmidt et al., 2014).

Recommended by NICE and used in services in United Kingdom and internationally (Adamson et al., 2019; Byrne et al., 2017; Giel et al., 2015; Schmidt et al., 2012; Schmidt et al., 2015; Schmidt et al., 2016; Startup et al. 2021; Wade et al., 2011; Wittek et al., 2023), MANTRA remains relatively understudied. It is mainly applied in adult but also in adolescent (Quiles et al., 2021; Wittek et al., 2023), with varying session numbers and formats, individually and in groups, and from different settings (Adamson et al., 2019;

Giel et al., 2015; Schmidt et al., 2015; Wittek et al., 2023). No review to date has investigated MANTRA across these different conditions, therefore, the aim of this study is to systematically update the research evidence regarding the use of Maudsley Model of Anorexia Nervosa Treatment for Adults (MANTRA), in the treatment of Eating Disorders (ED) and to contribute to our understanding of the treatment's effectiveness.

2. METHOD

The protocol for the systematic review was registered with Open Science Framework (OSF) on June 11th, 2023 (<https://osf.io/4b2xv/>). The systematic review was conducted in accordance with the PRISMA 2020 Statement (Page et al., 2021) by two researchers (YQ and SF).

2.1 Literature Search

A comprehensive search of the Web of Science, Scopus, and PsycInfo databases was carried out. Additionally, we extended the search to clinical registries, including PROSPERO and OSF, to identify ongoing and recently completed research. To ensure inclusivity, we thoroughly examined references cited in all articles, aligning or not with our inclusion criteria. The search was restricted to articles published in either Spanish or English from January 2010 to May 2023.

2.2 Eligibility criteria

The descriptors used were “Mantra”, “Maudsley Model of Anorexia Nervosa Treatment for Adults”, “eating disorders”, “anorexia”, “bulimia” and “disordered eating”. This study focused on identifying published articles discussing the usefulness of MANTRA in treating for ED. We adhered to modified PICOS criteria as proposed by Liberati et al. (2009), outlined in Table 1. A comprehensive array of physical variables and psychiatric disorders was considered, such as BMI, eating disorder symptoms, depression, anxiety, stress, obsessive compulsive disorder, and clinical impairment.

Insert Table 1

Studies were included if they were:

- a) Empirical research articles.
- b) Written in English and Spanish.
- c) Recruiting patients (adolescents, young adults or adults) with an ED.
- d) Investigated the application of MANTRA or an adaptation.
- e) Included all type of designs.
- f) Reported pre- and post-intervention MANTRA outcomes.

Studies were excluded if they were:

- a) Patient, family, or professional narratives.
- b) Not reporting MANTRA outcomes.
- c) Qualitative studies.
- d) Single case studies.
- e) Literature review studies.

2.3 Data extraction and risk of bias assessment

Initially, studies were selected based on titles and abstracts by two researchers (YQ and SF). Duplicate references were discarded, and articles were screened based on inclusion/exclusion criteria. After this phase, the researchers reviewed the full text of the remaining articles. Discrepancies were resolved by a third researcher (AR).

Details were extracted regarding design, sample size, population characteristics, interventions, and outcome assessments. The synthesis of the data was grouped by BMI, eating disorder symptomatology and emotional state, and other outcome variables. The risk of bias in each study was assessed using the Cochrane tools (Higgins et al., 2019). Different tools were used for randomised and non-randomised studies. Disagreements were resolved via discussion with a third researcher (AR).

3. RESULTS

3.1 Study Selection

Initially, 148 articles were identified from the selected databases. Duplicate articles (n = 68) were then eliminated. After screening, 64 articles were eliminated: theoretical approach (n = 35); other types of studies (n = 8); patient experiences (n = 5); study protocol (n = 5); therapist experiences (n = 2); poster, book review (n = 2); other interventions (n = 2); family intervention (n = 1); single case (n = 1); and other (n = 3). Process is shown in Figure 1.

From 16 articles reviewed by abstract, three were not selected. They were discarded because they didn't provide original data from the application of MANTRA (n = 1), narrated patient experience (n = 1) or was a single case study (n = 1). From the 13 full-text articles, four were discarded for: not providing data on preliminary study evidence (study protocol) (n = 1), comparing data from previous studies carried out by other authors (n = 2), and not specifying sufficient quantitative data (n = 1). Finally, 9 studies were selected for the review. However, the publications by Schmidt et al., (2015) and Schmidt et al., (2016) represent the pre-post intervention and follow-up, respectively, of the same study.

Insert Figure 1

3.2 Descriptive characteristics of included studies

Table 2 provides some key characteristics of the included studies. The studies were published between 2011 to 2023. Most interventions were implemented in the United Kingdom (n = 5), also in Australia (n = 2), Austria (n = 1), and Germany (n = 1). Most studies were conducted in multidisciplinary centers with outpatients, except for one with inpatients (Adamson et al., 2019) and another study conducted in a hospital with outpatients (Giel et al., 2015).

In terms of study design, four were randomised controlled trials (RCTs), three had a case series design, one was a non-randomized controlled clinical trial, and one was a cohort study. The RCTs included sample sizes from 34 to 72 patients, case series from 12 to 33 patients, the non-randomized controlled clinical trial had 31 and 152 in each group, and the cohort study had 45 and 47.

The articles were published over a decade (2011 to 2023). The studies applied similar criteria for the diagnosis of ED, mostly DSM-IV and in one case ICD-10 (Startup et al., 2021). In all studies, participants had a diagnosis of AN, except in Startup et al. (2021) where Other Specified Feeding or Eating Disorders (OSFED) were also included. The minimum and maximum values of the mean BMI ranged from 13.7 to 18.5.

The samples were mostly composed of women who were receiving or starting treatment in specialised ED services, except for the outpatient treatment by videoconference in the study by Giel et al., (2015). Five studies involved both women and men, but the proportion of men was much lower, with 10.3% being the highest percentage of men (Startup et al., 2021). No gender-differentiated analyses were carried out. All studies were

conducted with adults except Wittek et al. (2023) with adolescents, applying an adaptation of MANTRA called MANTRAA. Participant ages ranged from 13 to 54 years. Regarding the interventions applied, in four studies intervention sessions were based only on MANTRA (Byrne et al., 2017; Giel et al., 2015; Schmidt et al., 2012; Schmidt et al., 2015; Schmidt et al., 2016) or MANTRAA (Wittek et al., 2023), while three studies applied MANTRA with usual treatment (Adamson et al., 2019; Startup et al., 2021; Wade et al., 2011). Specifically, it was combined with motivational interviewing (5-8 sessions) (Wade et al., 2011), individual sessions (2-8) in addition to MANTRA group sessions (Startup et al., 2021), or combined with treatment as usual (TAU) and with the specific family treatment ECHO (Experienced Carers Helping Others) (Adamson et al., 2019). Most applied between 20 and 30 sessions (Schmidt et al., 2012; Schmidt et al., 2015; Schmidt et al., 2016; Startup et al., 2021; Wade et al., 2011). Byrne et al., (2017) had 25 to 40 sessions, and Giel et al., (2015) had 10 sessions. The minimum number of sessions was 5 in the study of Adamson et al., (2019). The average duration was 4-6 months in most studies (Startup et al., 2021; Giel et al., 2015; Schmidt et al., 2012; Schmidt et al., 2015; Schmidt et al., 2016; Wittek et al., 2023), except 10 months in Byrne et al. (2017) and Wade et al. (2011). Adamson et al. (2019) indicated the duration by days of treatment: 88 days in the ECHO MANTRA plus TAU condition and 122 days in TAU condition, approximately three months.

In all studies, MANTRA was applied individually, except in Startup et al., (2021) where it was applied in a group. In Giel et al. (2015), of the 10 sessions applied, two were face to face and the rest online.

In terms of outcome variables, all studies included eating symptomatology assessed using the Eating Disorder Examination Questionnaire (EDE-Q) or the Eating Disorder Examination Interview (EDE), and BMI or weight. Emotional state assessment was included in seven studies using the Hospital Anxiety Depression Scale (HADS) (Adamson et al., 2019; Schmidt et al., 2012; Wade et al., 2011), the Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale-21 (DASS-21) (Byrne et al., 2017; Schmidt et al., 2015; Schmidt et al., 2016), Structured Clinical Interview for DSM (SCID-I) (Giel et al., 2015), State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) and Beck Depression Inventory-2 (BDI-2) (Wittek et al., 2023).

Additional variables included motivation to change with the Anorexia Nervosa Stages Of Change Questionnaire (ANSOCQ) (Wade et al., 2011; Wittek et al., 2023), clinical impairment with the Clinical Impairment Questionnaire (CIA) (Byrne et al., 2017; Schmidt et al., 2015; Schmidt et al., 2016; Schmidt et al., 2012), obsessive compulsive disorder with the Obsessive Compulsive Inventory-Revised (OCI-R) (Schmidt et al., 2015; Schmidt et al., 2016; Schmidt et al., 2012; Wittek et al., 2023), Credibility and Expectations Questionnaire (CEQ) (Byrne et al., 2017) and self-esteem with the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (Wade et al., 2011).

Some studies included neurocognitive scales. Schmidt et al. (2012) used the Brixton Spatial Anticipation Task (BSAT), the Wisconsin Card Sorting Task (WCST), and Trail Making Task (TMT). Schmidt et al., (2015) used the Rey-Osterrieth Complex Figure Test, Reading the Mind in Films Task, BSAT and WCST.

In the studies by Schmidt et al. (2012), Schmidt et al. (2015), and Schmidt et al. (2016), the control group received Specialist Supportive Clinical Management (SSCM), also considered as Treatment as Usual (TAU). In Adamson et al. (2019), the control group underwent TAU. In Byrne et al.'s (2017) study, the comparison groups received SSCM and Enhanced Cognitive Behavior Therapy (CBT-E) treatment. In Wittek et al. (2023), the Treatment as Usual with Other (TAU-O) condition involved any specific therapeutic

intervention, such as cognitive-behavioural therapy, systemic family therapy, psychodynamic or psychoanalytic therapy, or humanistic approaches.

Insert Table 2

3.3 Risk of bias

Figure 2 details the risk of bias assessment. RCTs exhibited low risk of bias, meeting all criteria (Schmidt et al., 2012; 2015; 2016), except the Byrne et al. (2017) study, which did not comply with 'Blinding of outcome assessment'. In contrast, case series, non-randomized controlled clinical trials (NRCT), and cohort studies had a high risk of bias. Wade et al. (2011) met criteria for blinding of outcome assessment, blinding of outcome data, and incomplete outcome data. The bias was determination is in Figure 2.

Insert Figure 2

3.4 BMI

Seven of eight studies analysed BMI differences pre- and post-treatment. Adamson et al. (2019) considered weight instead of BMI. Five of seven MANTRA interventions showed statistically significant BMI improvements before and after treatment. Wittek et al. (2023), with the MANTRAa, found significant changes at 18-month follow-up ($p = .001$, $d = 0.84$). Startup et al. (2021) observed changes at 6-month follow-up ($t = -2.67$, $p = 0.01$), and Wade et al. (2011) at 12-month follow-up ($F = 7.32$, $p = .002$). Byrne et al. (2017) found significant BMI increases in all conditions ($F(3, 353.36) = 25$, $p < 0.001$). Schmidt et al. (2015; 2016) noted differences at 24 months in MANTRA ($z = 5.31$, $p < 0.001$, $ES = 1.83$) and SSCM ($z = 5.18$, $p < 0.001$, $ES = 1.75$). Giel et al. (2015), Adamson et al. (2019), and Schmidt et al. (2012) did not find significant BMI changes. Adamson et al. (2019) found significant weight increases over time ($F(49) = 45.02$, $p < 0.01$). RCT studies did not find BMI differences between treatment conditions (Byrne et al., 2017; Schmidt et al., 2012; 2015; 2016). Adamson et al. (2019) found no weight differences between MANTRA + TAU and TAU conditions. Wittek et al. (2023) found significant differences favoring MANTRAa over TAU-O for BMI-SDS ($F(3,168) = 3.209$, $p = 0.025$).

3.5 Eating disorder symptoms, emotional state and other variables

Regarding changes in *eating symptomatology* before and after the intervention, all the studies showed significant decrease in the mean scores. However, Giel et al. (2015) only found significant differences in the "eating concerns" subscale of the EDE.

In terms of differences depending on condition treatment, there were no statistically significant differences in the four RCTs in which it was compared. The experimental conditions were: MANTRA vs SSCM or CBT-E (Byrne et al., 2017) or MANTRA vs SSCM (Schmidt et al., 2012, Schmidt et al., 2015, Schmidt et al., 2016), regardless of the instrument used to assess it (EDE-Q and EDE). Only the study of Wittek et al. (2023) with the MANTRAa showed significant differences. There were statistically significant differences between groups for the total EDE score and three of its four subscales with better results for MANTRAa compared to TAU-O ($F(3,177) = 5.705$, $p = 0.001$).

Regarding *emotional state* and MANTRA, in five of the seven studies (four of them RCTs) in which it was evaluated, improvements were found after intervention with MANTRA (Adamson et al., 2019; Byrne et al., 2017; Schmidt et al., 2012; 2015; 2016). Wade et al., (2011) and Giel et al. (2015) found no differences in anxiety and depression in their case series designs studies. Respect to differences between condition treatments, no significant differences were found, except in the study by Byrne et al. (2017), in which

decrease in depression was higher with MANTRA ($F(6, 250.72) = 2.40, p < 0.003$). In the case of MANTRAa, state anxiety improved and no significant differences were found as a function of treatment condition.

Other variables assessed occasionally included motivation to change, obsessive-compulsive disorder, psychosocial impairment, and cognitive function. Wade et al. (2011) found a significant increase in motivation to change ($F = 4.36, p < .02, ES = 1.93$). Adamson et al. (2019) found no significant differences in the subscales importance and ability to change. Schmidt et al. (2015) found significant reductions in obsessive-compulsive disorder symptoms with MANTRA and SSCM, with better outcomes for SSCM at 24-month follow-up ($p = 0.04, d = 0.36$). Wittek et al. (2023) found no significant differences for this variable with MANTRAa.

Regarding psychosocial impairment, there was a statistically significant decrease after the intervention in two studies. The first, Schmidt et al., (2015), found differences between baseline and 12 months in MANTRA ($z = -5.44, p < 0.001$) and SSCM conditions ($z = -5.34, p < 0.001$). Similarly, Byrne et al., (2017), found that scores decreased significantly over time across all treatment's conditions ($F(3, 348.35) = 16.91, p < 0.001$), with no treatment by time interaction ($F(6, 348.35) = 1.48, p = 0.18$). Apart from this, there were no differences in work adjustment scores as measured by the Work and Social Adjustment Scale (WSAS) in Adamson et al., (2019).

Referring to cognitive function, there was an improvement in the MANTRA and SSCM conditions from baseline to 6-month follow-up assessed with the Rey-Osterrieth Complex Figure Test (Schmidt et al., 2015) (all $p < 0.05$), without differences between the two treatment conditions.

4. DISCUSSION

The aim to this study was to systematically update research on MANTRA and contribute to understanding its effectiveness. We examined its impact on BMI, eating symptomatology and emotional state, comparing it with other interventions. Results show that MANTRA is effective for improving BMI, eating disorder symptoms, and emotional state in adult AN patients. This suggests that MANTRA may be considered valid for treating these core symptoms of AN, however more research is needed to determine its effectiveness in treating cognitive and relational factors that maintain anorexia.

Overall, MANTRA could be considered as effective as other contrasted treatments (CBT and SSCM) since it obtains favourable results for the main clinical variables in AN such as BMI, eating disorder symptomatology and emotional state, and no differences were found between them. This would be in line with the results of Solmi's et al., (2021) meta-analysis which showed that there was no empirically supported psychosocial treatment for adults with AN with greater evidence than others. These results make us reflect on why MANTRA has not produced better results than the other treatments, when it is supposed that the other treatments have been adapted from treatments for other disorders or are less specific. MANTRA is unique in that it has been designed with the needs, characteristics and illness maintaining factors of anorexia in mind. This failure to differentiate between treatments may be because although these interventions are different and have specific protocols, there are several shared components among them. For example, all three approaches incorporate skill-building components aimed at equipping patients with coping strategies and adaptive skills to manage their symptoms and challenges associated with AN. These skills may include problem-solving, emotion regulation, assertiveness training, and relapse prevention techniques. In addition, all of them focus on psychoeducation. Psychoeducation helps patients understand their condition better and empowers them to actively engage in the treatment process. Each

approach involves setting specific, achievable goals for treatment. These goals may include behavioral changes (e.g., normalization of eating patterns, weight restoration), cognitive restructuring (e.g., challenging distorted thoughts about body image and food), and interpersonal improvements (e.g., enhancing social support networks). So, while each approach may have its theoretical underpinnings and specific techniques, these common components reflect the broader principles of evidence-based treatment for AN, emphasizing collaboration, psychoeducation, goal setting, monitoring, skill-building, and addressing comorbidities.

Perhaps MANTRA could be more successful if it was applied to specific patients or groups of patients who present the needs that MANTRA was designed to address. In addition to adult patients, it may be most beneficial for patients with interpersonal difficulties, with comorbidities, motivationally ambivalent or with neurocognition considerations. Another possible reason is that the number of MANTRA sessions applied in the reviewed studies never reached the stipulated maximum number, at 40. Only in Byrne's study was it indicated that between 25 and 40 were applied. In Adamson's study were 8, in Giel's 10, and in the rest of studies applied between 20 and 30 sessions (Schmidt et al., 2012; Schmidt et al., 2015; Schmidt et al., 2016; Startup et al., 2021; Wade et al., 2011). Perhaps a greater number of sessions would have produced better results.

MANTRA has been applied together with motivational interviewing (Wade et al., 2011), however, it has not shown better results than when it is applied alone. Perhaps the addition of Cognitive Remediation Therapy (CRT) (Tchanturia, 2014) would prove more successful, at least from a theoretical point of view, because CRT seems to intervene in an important module of the MANTRA. CRT aims to modify cognitive inflexibility and attention to detail, and it has offered promising findings in both adolescent and adult patients, as well as in both individual and group settings (Tchanturia et al., 2017).

The literature review has highlighted the different adaptations and variations that are being made with the MANTRA. It has been applied with different format (face-to-face or online), number of participants (individual or group), settings (inpatient or outpatient units), gender and age (adults or adolescents). This highlights its capacity to adapt and flexibility, however further research is needed to know its effectiveness with these variations. It is still premature to suggest that it can be applied in adolescents (MANTRAa) and with these different formats. Evaluation of MANTRA in these different formats is still ongoing but early evidence suggests positive effects.

4.1. Strengths and limitations

While comprehensive in its inclusion of all published studies meeting eligibility criteria, this review is limited by the lack of meta-analytic approach, which could not be done due to the scarcity of literature examining the effectiveness of MANTRA and the diversity of study design. High-quality studies, RCTs and, consequently, meta-analyses are difficult to complete for AN (Murray et al., 2019). Nevertheless, the narrative synthesis of the selected studies shows evidence for the effectiveness of MANTRA in patients with AN. The present study is based on a rigorous methodology and adopts a critical and up-to-date perspective to analyse the available evidence on this programme.

Limitations to interpreting this systematic review include the different methodological quality of included studies and the elevated risk of bias. Only the studies conducted by Schmidt et al. (2012; 2015; 2016) were not biased. Differences in study methodology varied, including 4 randomised controlled trials (RCTs), 3 case series designs, one non-randomised controlled study, and one cohort study. These last four studies have shown more problems with the methodological quality, including high risk of bias for allocation concealment, random generation, blinding of outcome assessment and blinding of participants and personnel. This low quality at the methodological level could indicate

low reliability of the results. These limitations are consistently reported in systematic reviews and meta-analyses examining treatment outcomes for AN (Murray et al., 2019). There were significant inconsistencies between studies in terms of sample size (ranging from 12 to 152 participants), assessment methodology (including primary outcomes and time between evaluations), duration, format (online vs. face to face), number of sessions applied, participant age (16-54), severity of the disorder, and different follow-up measures. The application of MANTRA also differed across studies, involving combinations with motivational interviewing (Wade et al., 2011), individual sessions + group format (Startup et al., 2021), TAU + MANTRA (Adamson et al., 2019) or adapted to the adolescent population (MANTRAa, Wittek et al., 2023). All these differences make it difficult to compare and generalise results across studies, representing one of the main limitations of this study.

Although the systematic review is a tool for standardising the results of the scientific literature, there are certain limitations inherent to the methodological process. For example, one of the limitations associated with the conduct of the review itself has to do with the selection of articles. This study is limited by the fact that only a few databases were reviewed. However, considering that therapies for eating disorders are a recent field of research that is still under investigation, we estimated that searching the main databases and considering that the number of duplicate articles was high (and therefore in other databases the articles might be similar), all relevant papers for this review should be included. In this sense, another bias, namely, “publication bias” should be considered, given that studies with more “favourable” results are more likely to be published. This may have conditioned the way the study was carried out and how the data were obtained. Another possible limitation of this systematic review is that “confirmation bias” may have occurred, since in all the selected articles authors of the MANTRA programme were involved in the intervention and the assessment of its effectiveness.

Despite these limitations we can conclude that MANTRA has the potential of primary outpatient treatment for AN patients. A remarkable point in favour of MANTRA is its protocolised intervention, which allows it to be easily replicated in different contexts, such as daycare centers or inpatient units (Ruiz et al., 2023). This, coupled with the favourable long-term results observed (e.g. at 24-month follow-up), is an essential feature due to the chronicity and recurrence of anorexia nervosa.

4.2 Guidelines for future research

This review points to some future challenges in the field of AN treatment. These include the design and implementation of randomised clinical trials (RCTs) that replicate the structure of previous studies. These include the use of protocolized sessions, assessment instruments and follow-up measures, as well as relating to the level of expertise and training of the psychotherapists in the specific treatment. Additionally, unifying the concept of recovery and being able to compare intervention groups with similar characteristics (e.g. duration of illness, care resources, type of main treatment) would include some of the objectives in order to obtain generalizable results.

In its current form, the MANTRA addresses issues and patients' characteristics relevant only to restrictive AN but not to binge/purge AN. Further research could construct MANTRA models for binge/purge disorders, and atypical AN. In addition, it would be valuable to determine the comparative efficacy of these interventions in different categories of patients, characterised by factors such as severity or duration of illness. In the context of adolescents or young adults with AN, investigation of the potential of MANTRAa as a complementary component of family therapy could provide significant data.

There is still a need for experimental and longitudinal studies to examine which components achieve better long-term outcomes on key treatment endpoints. Therefore, clarifying which first-choice treatments are effective, not only for intervention in adult anorexia nervosa, but for eating disorders in general, particularly when applied to populations with diverse characteristics, will bring us closer to clinical practice.

SUBMITTED

Highlights

- This systematic review is based on a rigorous methodology, following the recommendations of the PRISMA and PICOS guide to guarantee its rigor. It adopts a critical and up-to-date perspective to analyse the extensive number of studies that provide evidence on this programme.
- MANTRA appears to be as effective as CBT and SSCM for anorexia nervosa, showing favourable results in body mass index (BMI), eating disorder symptomatology and emotional state. More research is needed to establish its effectiveness in addressing the interpersonal and cognitive factors for which it was also designed.
- The adaptability of MANTRA is highlighted. It has been used in adolescent population, in group and online format, with inpatients and in males. However, more research is needed to determine its effectiveness.

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